

Mental Toughness and Psychological Well-being among National-Level Para-Athletes: The Moderating Role of Coaching Style

Akash Kumar, Chetna Jaiswal, Dharmendra Kumar Singh, Nishi Srivastava, and Zameel M M
Department of Psychology, Central University of South Bihar, Gaya

Athlete development in para-sport has progressed beyond a narrow emphasis on performance outcomes to incorporate psychological well-being as a key indicator of long-term success and sustainability. Para-athletes often encounter additional physical, social, and structural challenges, making the development of psychological resources particularly important for sustained engagement in competitive sport. Mental toughness is widely regarded as a vital psychological strength that enables para-athletes to manage competitive demands, persist through adversity, and adapt to intensive training environments. However, the extent to which mental toughness contributes to psychological well-being may be influenced by contextual factors within the sporting environment, particularly the coaching style experienced by para-athletes. The present study examines the association between mental toughness and psychological well-being and explores the role of coaching style as a moderator among national-level para-athletes. A cross-sectional design was applied, and data were collected by standardized questionnaires. The findings indicated a positive but weak correlation, suggesting that mental toughness contributes to well-being, but it's not the only dominant factor; there are also several other potential factors. And the coaching style was not found as a significant moderator between mental toughness and psychological well-being, showing there is an influence that may be indirect or situation-specific. The results highlighted the multifaceted role of psychological well-being among para-athletes towards the role of broader psychosocial factors. This study contributes to the growing literature on para-sport psychology in India and emphasizes the need for athlete-centered and context-sensitive interventions to enhance well-being among para-athletes.

Keywords: Coaching style, mental toughness, para-athletes, psychological well-being

Para-sport refers to the sports specifically designed for athletes with disabilities. In recent times, para-sport has gained participation and global attention due to its opportunities, visibility, and competitive

standards. After the Olympic Games and the Federation Internationale de Football Association (FIFA) World Cup, the Paralympics have developed into the third-largest athletic event in the world (Darcy et al., 2017). Over the past fifty years, the Paralympic, or Parallel, Games for athletes with disabilities have been crucial in shifting perceptions of disability and advancing the inclusion agenda (Gold & Gold, 2007). In parathletes, along with their physical health, their psychological strength also matters the most for their overall well-being. Para-athletes often experience stressors, like training limitations, pressure, societal barriers, which may influence their mental health and overall, their quality of life.

The concept of psychological well-being is complex and includes emotional, cognitive, and motivational-behavioural aspects of human existence. It is more than just the absence of mental disease; rather, it is a positive condition of mental health marked by a feeling of purpose, personal development, and life satisfaction. This idea has its roots in psychological theories of optimal functioning and is impacted by a complex interaction of biological, psychological, social, and cultural elements. For athletes, well-being is not only for sustaining motivation and confidence but also handles stress, setbacks, transition in sports. Among para-athletes, psychological well-being may be shaped by both sport-related factors and psychological experiences such as inclusion and social support.

Another key psychological attribute is Mental toughness that support athletes in coping with pressure and competitive demands and expectations. Mental toughness includes components such as confidence, control, and constancy. This Mental toughness plays a

Author Note

Akash Kumar, Research Scholar, Department of Psychology
Central University of South Bihar, Gaya, Bihar
ORCID ID: 0009-0008-3253-1822

Dr. Chetna Jaiswal, Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology
Central University of South Bihar, Gaya, Bihar
E-mail: chetna@cusb.ac.in
ORCID ID: 0009-0006-4718-5681

Prof. Dharmendra Kumar Singh, Department of Psychology
Central University of South Bihar, Gaya, Bihar
E-mail: dharmendrkr@cusb.ac.in
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-8371-6482

Nishi Srivastava, Research Scholar, Department of Psychology
Central University of South Bihar, Gaya, Bihar
E-mail: nishisrivastava300@gmail.com
ORCID ID: 0009-0001-4436-3618

Zameel M M, Master's Student, Department of Psychology, Central
University of South Bihar, Gaya, Bihar
ORCID ID: 0009-0001-5322-1232
E-mail: zameelmami@gmail.com

We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to
Akash Kumar, Research Scholar, Department of Psychology
Central University of South Bihar, Gaya, Bihar
E-mail: akashkr@cusb.ac.in

vital role in the lives of para-athletes as it helps them juggle their physical pain, stigma, rehabilitation demands. Hence, it is important to explore whether mental toughness is associated with better psychological well-being among para-athletes.

Coaching style is another attribute that plays a central role in shaping athletes psychological experiences, training environment, and emotional regulation during sport participation. It also shapes the motivational climate and athlete confidence. Self-determination theory suggests that a supportive environment contributes to the well-being of athletes by satisfying basic needs such as autonomy, competence and relatedness (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Existing researches suggest that autonomy supportive coaching is linked with favourable growth and outcomes through need satisfaction processes (Coatsworth & Conroy, 2009). In para-sport, coaching style may be especially crucial because para-athletes depend upon coaches strategies skills and psychological reinforcement when facing competition and disability related challenges.

Despite the interest in mental toughness and athletes' well-being, research focusing specifically on para-athletes in India remains limited. Moreover, coaching style is recognised as an important psychological variable in sport, but its role as a moderator in the association of mental toughness and well-being is still understudied. Considering the importance of para-sport in India, there is a great need for research that identifies key psychological correlates that contribute to well-being among para-athletes.

Aim of the Study

- To examine the relation between mental toughness and psychological well-being among para-athletes.
- To assess the moderating role of coaching style on the association of mental toughness and psychological well-being.

Hypotheses of the Study

- Mental toughness would positively predict psychological well-being.
- Coaching style would moderate the relationship between mental toughness and psychological well-being.

Method

Participants

The sample comprised 25 National-level para-athletes who participated in the study. The participants were recruited from different para-sport settings across India through Purposive sampling. This sampling was considered based on the availability and willingness to take part in the study. The sample includes athletes from the Athletics discipline of Track and Field events.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Defined eligibility criteria and rejection standards were adopted to maintain the appropriateness and uniformity of the group.

Inclusion Criteria

- Para-athletes with a recognized disability status
- Participated at the National level in Para-sports

Exclusion Criteria

- Para-athletes who had not competed at the national level in para-sports
- Unwillingness to participate
- These parameters were instituted in order to ensure that the sample represents the intended population of competitive para-athletes.

Research Design

The present study adopts a quantitative, cross-sectional, and

correlational design to assess the association between Mental toughness and psychological well-being among Para-athletes. Further, the study tests whether coaching style moderates the relationship between mental toughness and psychological well-being.

Measures

Socio-demographic and Personal Data Sheet: A socio-demographic data sheet developed by the researcher was used to collect relevant background information from the participants.

Mental Toughness: Mental toughness was assessed using the sports Mental Toughness questionnaire developed by Sheard et al. (2009). This is a 14-item measure designed to assess mental toughness in sport settings. Higher scores indicate a higher level of mental toughness, while lower scores indicate a lower level. It comprises of three subscales: confidence, control, and constancy. The scale has demonstrated strong internal consistency ($\alpha > 0.80$) and validity across athletic populations.

Psychological Well-being Scale: The Psychological Well-being Scale was developed by Ryff and Keyes (1995) and used to assess para-athletes' overall well-being. There are six dimensions of this scale, i.e., Autonomy, Environmental Mastery, Personal Growth, Positive Relations with Others, Purpose in Life, and Self-acceptance. Cronbach's alpha values for the scale's six dimensions range from 0.70 to 0.80, indicating strong internal consistency.

Coaching Style: Coaching behaviour scale was developed by Üzüim et al. (2018) a 24-item questionnaire used to assess various aspects of coaching style. This scale evaluates three key characteristics: Knowledge and Skills, Being Fair, and Supportive Behaviour, where "Characteristic Features" has a consistency value of 0.88, "Knowledge and Skills Accumulation" has a value of 0.86, and "Being Fair" has a value of 0.56.

Procedure

Participants were informed about the objectives of the study, and a good rapport was built before data collection. Informed consent was taken from all participants, and standardized questionnaires were provided with guidance. Data were analyzed using SPSS.

Cultural Adaptation and Validation

All scales were translated into Hindi and reviewed by language experts to ensure language accuracy and cultural fit.

Results

Table 1

Socio-demographic Profile of Participants

Variable	Sub-variable	N	N (%)
Gender	Male	21	84
	Female	4	16
Marital Status	Married	3	12
	Unmarried	22	88
Work outside sports	Yes	6	24
	No	19	76
Level of participation	National	23	92
	International	2	8
Type of Disability	Acquired	13	52
	By birth	12	48

The sample consisted of a total of 25 para-athletes. With a mean range of 23.28 years ($SD= 5.14$), ranging from 17 to 33 years. In terms of gender, 84% were male, while 16% were female. Most of the participants were Unmarried ($n=22, 88\%$), while 3 participants (12%) were unmarried. Regarding employment status, 6 participants (24%) were working outside sport activities, while 19 (76%) others were not. Out of 25, 23 participants (92%) competed at the national level while 2 participants (8%) competed at the international level. Regarding disability type, 13 participants (52%) had reported acquired disability, while 12 participants (48%) reported having disability by birth.

Table 2

Correlation among Mental Toughness, Psychological Well-being, and Coaching Style

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3
1. Mental Toughness (MT)	43.52	5.84	-		
2. Well-Being (WB)	93.60	15.32	.210	-	
3. Coaching Style (CS)	85.36	7.33	.365	.334	-

Note. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$

In Table 2, Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to show the association between mental toughness, well-being, and coaching style. It was hypothesized (H1) that mental toughness would be positively associated with psychological well-being, and the Results indicate that there is a positive correlation between mental toughness and psychological well-being ($r = .21, p = .314$). However, the association was not statistically significant, which shows that H1 was not supported. Mental toughness was also correlated positively with coaching style ($r = .37, p = .073$). Coaching style also showed a positive correlation with psychological well-being ($r = .33, p = .103$). Overall, the correlations were positive, but none of them were statistically significant.

Table 3

Moderation Analysis using Mental Toughness as Predictor variable, Coaching Style as Moderator and Well-being as Criterion Variable among Para-athletes

Predictor	B	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	93.55	25.50	.000	85.92	101.18
MTT (A)	0.26	0.36	.726	-1.28	1.81
CST (B)	0.63	0.93	.365	-0.79	2.05
A × B	0.004	0.03	.976	-0.23	0.24

Note. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$

Table 3 shows the moderation analysis conducted to examine whether coaching style moderates the relationship between mental toughness and psychological well-being. It was hypothesized (H2) that coaching style would moderate the relationship between mental toughness and psychological well-being. The analysis was done using Hayes' PROCESS macro (model1), where mental toughness was entered as the independent variable(X), psychological well-being as the dependent variable(Y), and the coaching style as the moderating variable(W). Overall model explains $R^2 = .12$ of variance in psychological well-being and was not significant, $F(3, 21) = 0.80, p = .507$. The interaction term (Mt × Cs) was not found statistically significant ($b = 0.004, SE = 0.115, t = 0.03, p = 0.976$). This indicates that coaching style did not moderate the relationship

between mental toughness and psychological well-being, which shows that H2 was not supported.

Discussion

The present study aimed to examine the relationship between mental toughness, coaching style and well-being. And to test whether the coaching style moderates the relationship between mental toughness and well-being among para-athletes. The findings indicated a positive association between mental toughness and psychological well-being, but the relationship was not significant. Even the coaching style showed a positive association with psychological well-being; however, the relationship was not significant. The moderation analysis results revealed that coaching style did not moderate the relationship between mental toughness and psychological well-being.

The absence of a significant interaction effect does not suggest that the coaching style is unimportant, but it reflects the sample-related and design-related limitations that influence the statistical outcome. First, the non-significant interaction effect may be attributed to a small sample size, which reduces statistical power and weakens the ability to detect the moderation effect. The second factor can be limited variance, as most athletes rated coaching style similarly, so the moderation effects cannot be adequately seen. Thirdly, the psychological well-being may depend on more factors than just mental toughness and coaching style, like stigma, ableism, life satisfaction, social support, etc. Finally, the cross-sectional design of the study limits causal interpretation and captures only one moment, which hinders the changes in well-being in different training phases, where the moderating role of coaching style might be more visible. Previous existing literature shows that there are mixed findings, where the studies suggests that Mental toughness showed moderate to strong relation with well-being (Stamp et al., 2015) while in one study (Sohrabi et al., 2017) shows a weak positive correlation between psychological well-being and mental toughness, suggesting that higher mental toughness is associated with marginally higher levels of well-being. These studies contribute to the growing evidence suggesting that the relationship between mental toughness and well-being may be influenced by more than one factor, such as mental toughness and coaching style.

In the context of Indian para-athletes, the present study suggests several practical implications for coaching practices and the athlete support system. Coaches should focus not only on winning but also on the mental support of para-athletes. Mental toughness development interventions should be added to para-athletes' training programmes to strengthen psychological readiness. Workshops regarding stress management and confidence building can empower para-athletes to maintain their well-being during training and competition.

Despite the contribution, the present study has certain limitations that should be acknowledged in future studies. Future studies may address these limitations by including a larger sample to improve generalizability, and a longitudinal design should be used to better understand directionality and change over time by moving beyond one-time data collection. Other variables should be included, such as burnout, social support, and ableism, to show the influence of these factors on psychological well-being. Future research can build more inclusive, context-sensitive models in relevance to Indian para-athletes.

Conclusion

The present study examined mental toughness, well-being, and coaching style. The coaching style was tested as a moderator. The findings showed a positive correlation between mental toughness and well-being. However, the association was insignificant, and the coaching style did not moderate the well-being and mental toughness relationship, which aligns with the existing findings, where it was shown that there is a weak to moderate relationship between mental toughness and well-being. This study adds evidence to the limited research on para-athletes, especially where psychological variables such as mental toughness, well-being, and coaching style are understudied. Moreover, the study emphasizes the importance of an athlete-centered approach that prioritizes the athlete's well-being alongside athletic performance.

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Received December 16, 2025

Revision received December 29, 2025

Accepted January 2, 2026